

EFFECTIVENESS OF COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT FOR HEEL SPUR

Tuksanova Zebiniso Izatulloevna

Rajabova Surayyo Hikmatovna

Bukhara State Medical Institute, Uzbekistan

Resume. This article provides information on the epidemiology, etiological factors, pathogenetic mechanism, clinical symptoms, and treatment methods of heel fasciitis. Also, in the treatment of this pathology, the use of physiotherapeutic procedures recommended by us, taking into account their compatibility with each other, and the study of the dynamics of the results with important features describing the course of the disease.

Key words: heel fasciitis, physical therapy, obesity, therapeutic exercises, flat heel, pulse wave therapy, laser therapy.

Relevance. Heel fasciitis is a disease characterized by inflammation of tendons, ligaments and muscles located in the heel area. As a result of inflammation, tumors begin to form in the heel bones. These tumors also damage the soft tissues due to their enlargement, which causes pain and severe discomfort when walking or standing on the heel. In most cases, the heel spur is the result of involutional processes of the human body, and can also occur as an anatomical feature in middle-aged and elderly people.

According to statistics, more than 10% of patients who come to us with diseases of the locomotor system suffer from this disease. The prevalence of heel spurs is 22-30% among people aged 25-45.

There are several factors that cause this disease, which are diseases of the musculoskeletal system, flat heels, obesity, gout, atherosclerosis of the leg veins,

arthritis, Bekhterev's disease, microtraumas on the heel and genetic predisposition.

One of the main reasons for complaints is pain in the heel area. In the early stages of the disease, pain usually occurs when walking, standing up from a chair or bed. During the day, the pain subsides a little, and at the end of the day it gets worse. Later, the symptom of pain is constant, and it bothers the patient not only when walking, but also at rest.

Pain in the heel has a burning character and is sharp when leaning on the heel. The pain can spread over the entire surface of the heel. Pain can appear suddenly and have an acute character, or it can develop slowly and become chronic.

Purpose of work. **D** is to provide comprehensive treatment to patients with plantar fasciitis and justify it in order to increase the effectiveness of treatment . It also consists of a comparative study of the dynamics of indicators that improve the quality of life of patients after the recommended physiotherapy and therapeutic exercises.

Materials and methods. 57 (34 in the main group, 23 in the comparison group) patients (average age 43.9) who applied to the rheumatology, traumatology and physiotherapy departments of the Bukhara regional multidisciplinary medical center were involved in the research with their consent.

In order to solve the research tasks, instrumental, functional and statistical methods of research and analysis were used, and they were analyzed using medical statistical and mathematical methods.

Before and after the treatment, the thickness of the heel aponeurosis was determined by digital radiography of the patients.

In the analysis of factors causing heel fasciitis, the greatest indicator showed a flat heel (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Factors causing heel fasciitis

The main group of patients suffering from plantar fasciitis was treated with pulse wave therapy, laser treatment, and therapeutic exercises from physiotherapeutic treatments. In the comparison group, only physiotherapeutic procedures were recommended.

The therapeutic pressure of pulse wave therapy (BTL-6000) treatment for patients in both groups is 2-2.5 Bar, frequency - 10-15 Hz, taking into account the area of the pathological process in one session, i.e. up to 500 pulses to the areas with severe pain, in order to create adaptation in the patient. ; and in relatively painful areas - up to 1500 pulses were given. Each patient was treated separately. The course of treatment was selected individually depending on the stage of the disease.

Laser therapy treatment was recommended to patients in both groups after pulse wave therapy. A frequency of 80-90 Hz and a current of 90-100 mW were administered to both groups of patients for 10 minutes every day for 10 days.

The main group of patients was given additional treatment exercises. The recommended treatment is the nature of the exercises and the way they are performed individually. Treatment exercises were gradually increased. The exercises were performed 1-3 times on the first day, and 3-5 times on the second day, and their duration was gradually increased and performed regularly. The

results were observed dynamically for 3, 6 months.

The results obtained. Patients who participated in the survey were divided into 2 groups in a representative manner. When analyzed by gender, they were found in the following proportions in both groups: female patients (79.4%; 78.3%), male patients (20.6%; 21.7%). Widespread among women compared to men , one of the factors that cause this pathology can be attributed to the fact that women wear high-heeled shoes.

We conducted a survey of patients with plantar fasciitis using the FHSQ scale. Improvement was noted in 48 patients, and no change in 9 patients. The rate of no change in patients is related to the duration of the disease.

The questionnaire was created to reflect the quality of life of patients with foot diseases. It contains 13 questions and is divided into 4 groups: heel pain (4 questions), heel function (4 questions), shoes (3 questions) and general condition of the heel (2 questions). The final score was calculated by the program from 0 to 100, where 100 was considered good compensation. If more than half of the responses in one of the groups are missing, then the average values are calculated. The time interval was 1 week.

Pain in the heel area was determined using the VASh scale in the morning, in the evening, at rest and while walking.

Both groups had a significant improvement in the evaluation parameters (morning and evening pain) after 3 and 6 months compared to baseline ($P<0.001$). But after treatment, some parameters in group 2 did not show significant differences compared to their initial values ($P<0.05$).

Due to the fact that only physiotherapeutic procedures were recommended to the patients of the comparison group, it was observed that their changes were lower than the results of the first group of patients.

The feasibility of developing differentiated rehabilitation methods for patients with plantar fasciitis was evaluated using a quality of life study. After

treatment with physical factors and exercise, patients with plantar fasciitis did not experience any deterioration in quality of life on any scale.

The reliability of the differences in the average values of the studied parameters in comparison with the initial values is as follows: $p < 0.05$.

It was found that the quality of life of patients improved significantly in all scales. At the same time, after a complex rehabilitation course, a significant improvement of indicators of both physical and psychological components of the quality of life was found in patients suffering from plantar fasciitis. It is worth noting that the greatest dynamics in terms of physical component indicators were established in the life activity scales.

Summary. The therapeutic effect of complex rehabilitation methods was found in patients with a significant decrease in the intensity of pain in the heel area during rest and movement, and a positive change in the quality of life. Taking into account the compatibility of the physiotherapeutic and therapeutic exercises recommended by us, the treatments have given a significant effect.

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